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PRINCIPLES FOR DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY OF STATIONS PROVIDING SERVICE TO PASSENGER TRANSPORT IN THE URGANCH CITY

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Abstract: *In this article, 19 bus routes in the city of Urgench were selected as the object of research. According to the results of experimental studies, based on the flow intensity in 19 routes, the reliability probability of the stops at a level of 0.95 was calculated. As a result, it was found that 5 stops in the forward direction and 3 in the reverse direction were inefficient, and 3 stops in the forward direction and 4 in the reverse direction were operating with excessive voltage.*

Keywords: *Urban transport, speed, passenger and freight transport, road network, passenger flow, mathematical expectation, dispersion, ecology.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the state of urban transport systems does not meet the needs of modern society. The transition to a market economy led to changes in the operation of urban transport systems. Transport problems are most acute in large cities, where the loss of travel time due to the increase in cars significantly exceeds the permissible standards, the carrying capacity of urban passenger transport inevitably decreases. [1].

The most reasonable option of urban transport systems is determined by the following criteria: travel time, cargo carrying capacity, interchange,

economic indicators; characteristics of the transport system by types of transport, their carrying capacity, distance, speed of vehicles, distribution of passenger and cargo volumes; can be used as a collective concept that also includes the characteristics of the road network.[2, 3].

The level of public satisfaction with the work of urban transport systems is the main indicator of the quality of the entire system, but this indicator has not been studied in practice. Undoubtedly, all sub-systems of urban transport systems should be considered together, including: urban passenger and freight management practices, traffic organization, while taking into account

environmental criteria. Any solution in the field of urban transport systems should be based on the study of passenger-cargo communications and the design of the development of the transport network.

Materials and methods used

Many problems can arise in the processes of collecting and processing data on passenger flows. The parameters of providing transport services to passenger flows are diverse, most of them are random in nature. When using a selective method of studying passenger flows or analyzing the process of providing transport services to them, it is important to calculate the reliability limits of their various parameters.

The flow of passengers determined at a certain point of the street network was monitored for time T. If the speed of the passenger flow of the transport service is N and the probability of the number of n passengers counted during the time T is P, then it is reasonable to consider the passenger flow as a Poisson flow at a low indicator level. [3].

In that case

$$P_n = \frac{(NT)^n}{n!} e^{-NT} \quad (1)$$

For Poisson flow, the average number of passengers transported is μ and σ

the variance is the same:

$$\mu = \sigma^2 = NT, \quad (2)$$

that is, the ratio of the average mathematical deviation to the average value is equal to:

that is, the ratio of the average mathematical deviation to the average value is equal to:

$$\frac{\sigma}{\mu} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{NT}} \quad (3)$$

To select the value of $T \sigma/\mu$ it is necessary to give some restrictions to For example, if we take the upper limit of this ratio as 0.5, then it is necessary to calculate $NT > 500$, that is, 500 passengers.

During the investigation of the flow of passengers carried in the city public transport, it became known that the time interval between the vehicles carrying passengers corresponds to the Erlang distribution of order k ($k > 1$), the speed of the vehicles carrying the flow of passengers is large. when ($k=1$) obeys the exponential distribution corresponding to the Poisson distribution. In this case, σ/μ is defined as follows:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma}{\mu}\right)_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{kNT}} \quad (4)$$

It can be seen from this expression that as the value of k increases, the arrival distribution of vehicles carrying the flow of passengers decreases. In

addition, the value of k varies depending on various factors, therefore, expression (3) is used in some cases. It can be concluded that a large number of measurements are required to study the speed of the passenger flow in the high-level transport service.

In order to calculate passenger flows, let m series measurements with $n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m$ series results with the time interval between each measurement equal to T be carried out. The interval between vehicles carrying passenger flows is an independent random variable that obeys the laws of Erlang distribution when $k \geq 1$. Based on the Central Limit Theorem, it is worth noting that if the passenger volume of the NT transport service is very large, then each obeys the normal distribution:

$$f(n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\mu}} \exp\left\{-\frac{n-\mu^2}{2\mu}\right\}, \quad (\mu = 100) \quad (5)$$

It should be noted that both distributions are almost identical.

That's it

because in the future the quantity n_i will have a normal distribution with mean NT and NT/k , $k \geq 1$.

Let the results of calculating the speed of the passenger flow of the transport service in the series $n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m$ be that the time interval between each of them lasts T , the indices

correspond to different time intervals that do not correspond to each other:

$$f(n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma}} \exp\left\{-\frac{(n-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right\}, \quad (6)$$

Here μ – average and σ^2 – variance (such as a normal distribution $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ we express through.

Measuring the flow rate of passengers provided by the transport service is nothing more than estimating the quantity $\mu = (NT)$ according to random variables $n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m$ whose values are uniformly distributed.

If μ and σ^2 are not mixed with the variance of the mathematical expectation estimate m and the minimum variance of sampling from the population σ^2 , expression (6) obeys the probability distribution of the density, then we have:

$$\hat{\mu} = \bar{n} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m n_i; \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}^2 = \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{i=1}^m (n_i - \mu)^2; \quad (8)$$

$$t = \frac{n-\mu}{\hat{\sigma}/\sqrt{m}}; \quad (9)$$

In fact, while t does not obey a normal distribution, σ itself is a random variable, it is known that t obeys a t -Student distribution with the following density:

$$f(t) = \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\varphi+1}{2}\right)}{\sqrt{\varphi\pi} \Gamma\left(\frac{\varphi}{2}\right)} \left(1 + \frac{t^2}{\varphi}\right)^{-(\varphi+1)/2} \quad (10)$$

here φ number of free pointers, it will be equal to the following value.

$\varphi = k!1$, a Γ gamma function (aggregate factorial).

As before, φ for t_0 if we define,

$$\alpha = 2 \int_0^{\infty} f(t) dt, \quad (11)$$

then the confidence limits are given by the following expressions:

$$\mu_t = n - \frac{\hat{\sigma}}{\sqrt{m}} t_0; \quad \mu_U = n - \frac{\hat{\sigma}}{\sqrt{m}} t_0; \quad (12)$$

α value t_0 corresponding to a given φ can also be calculated, but it takes different values for different free exponents.

According to the results of the research, the 19th bus route was taken as the research object from the inner city routes in Urganch, which in turn transported a total of 370 passengers in the right direction. lib, they are distributed over 13 stops as follows: 15,42, 35, 18, 12, 16, 17, 36, 38, 24, 27, 37,53.

A total of 330 passengers were transported in the reverse direction, and the flow of passengers was distributed over 12 stops as follows: 35, 32, 28, 22, 34, 27, 25, 22, 28, 17, 24, 36.

We calculate confidence intervals with a confidence probability of 0.95.

In the case of the right direction $m=13$ and $\alpha =3$.

Using formulas (7) and (8), we calculate the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= \bar{n} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m n_i = \frac{1}{13} 370 = 28,46; \\ \sigma^2 &= \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{i=1}^m (n_i - \mu)^2 = \frac{1}{12} 1919,23 = 159,93; \\ \sigma &= \sqrt{159,93} = 12.64. \end{aligned}$$

From the table, we determine that $t_0 = 2.1604$. Then, using the formula (12), we calculate the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_t (to'g'.y) &= n - \frac{\hat{\sigma}}{\sqrt{m}} t_0 = 28,46 - \frac{12,64}{\sqrt{13}} 2,1604 = 28,46 - 7,58 \approx 21; \\ \mu_u (to'g'.y) &= n + \frac{\hat{\sigma}}{\sqrt{m}} t_0 = 28,46 + \frac{12,64}{\sqrt{13}} 2,1604 = 28,46 + 7,58 \approx 37. \end{aligned}$$

In the reverse direction, $m=30$ and $\varphi=3$. We do the same calculations as above:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= \bar{n} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m n_i = \frac{1}{12} 330 = 27,5; \\ \sigma^2 &= \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{i=1}^m (n_i - \mu)^2 = \frac{1}{12} 381 = 31,75; \\ \sigma &= \sqrt{31,75} = 5.63. \end{aligned}$$

From the table, we determine that $t_0 = 2.1604$. Then, using the formula (12), we calculate the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_t (tesk.y) &= n - \frac{\hat{\sigma}}{\sqrt{m}} t_0 = 27,5 - \frac{5,63}{\sqrt{12}} 2,1788 = 27,5 - 3,55 \approx 24; \\ \mu_u (tesk.y) &= n + \frac{\hat{\sigma}}{\sqrt{m}} t_0 = 27,5 + \frac{5,63}{\sqrt{12}} 2,1788 = 27,5 + 3,55 \approx 31. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the lower limit of the reliability interval for calculating passenger flows in the correct direction on bus route 19 is 21 and the upper limit is 37. In the reverse direction of this bus route, the lower confidence limit is 24 and the upper limit is 31.

Results

As a result, it was found that 5 stations in the right direction and 3 stations in the opposite direction are ineffective, and 3 stations in the right direction and 4 stations in the opposite direction are working with excess voltage. It is necessary to consider the issue of closing the inefficiently working stations and separating them because the stations with a value greater than the upper limit are working with great effort. If it is not possible to close the stops, merge them with the neighboring stop or split them

into two, then it will be necessary to reconsider the bus stop time at these stops.

Summary

The appeals, proposals and recommendations received by the "Transport Department" of Khorezm region, as well as the scheme of new routes developed by experts are presented in Figure 1. The recommendations developed in this figure 1 are sufficiently developed measures to modernize the internal routes of the city of Urganch, as well as the need to open 2 new routes in the ring road part of the city in this proposal, taking into account the passenger flow here It is expected that the level of passenger service will increase by opening new routes around the central Farmer's market in Oq-Oltin and Goybu neighborhoods of Urganch District.

Picture 1. Proposal project of new routes to be opened in Urganch city

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